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Title: STRESS-Mums Project for a lone mothers' inclusive citizenship: findings from the first fieldwork

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STRESS-Mums research study has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no 843976. This study aims to investigate the lone mothers' everyday strategies and social practices to negotiate (or not negotiate) the dominant definition of family and parenthood proposed by institutions and professionals, and the less legitimated and multiple situated definitions proposed by lone parents and embodied by their families. Furthermore, the study investigates how professionals do or do not negotiate these definitions of family and parenthood.

The research study focuses on the *transition* from double parenthood to lone motherhood, and, in particular, on the situation of judicial evaluation for child custody and courts' decisions for allowances and other obligations. This research considers the everyday strategies and social practices that lone mothers act and use to claim social inclusion in that transition as processes of 'active' social citizenship.

Using the approach of the Institutional Ethnography (IE), this project collects data in Belgium, Italy, Spain, and in the UK through discursive interviews to lone mothers, judicial professionals and gender issues activists, participant observations, document analysis, and photo-voice sessions involving mothers and professionals.

The paper presents the findings from the first fieldwork of this research study, that highlight how lone mothers are engaged in a struggle against the dominant definitions of family and parenthood with the aim of claiming social inclusion and reducing the negative effects of these definitions on their own future trajectories and for

their children. Since IE uses mapping as an important tool for visually representing and analyzing the concreteness of the everyday life of the participants, this presentation shows, through IE mapping, the practices of resistance of the mothers during their contacts with the judicial institutions in that transition period.

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